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The relationship between cultural intelligence and leadership Effectiveness of sport managers

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Abstract

Studies have shown that it essential for resolving of challenges of organizations, to have efficacy and effectiveness leadership and management. Therefore, the purpose of this research was to investigate the relationship between cultural intelligence and leadership effectiveness of sport managers. The Statistical popularity of this research was all managers of Sport and Young's Ministry , National Olympic committee, National Paralympics committee, National Olympic Academy, and Sport Federations (N=331). Base on Morgan table, 180 people were selected to this research. Saberi (1388) Leadership effectiveness questionnaire and Van Dyne and Ang Four Factor cultural intelligence scale questionnaire was used to collect data. Data analysis was performed by the Bivariate and multivariate regression. The results of present study showed that there was significant relationship between cultural intelligence and leadership effectiveness ($p<0/05$). Also, there was significant relationship between behavioral cultural intelligence and leadership effectiveness ($p<0/001$). Generally, this study showed that cultural intelligence is important factor in leadership effectiveness of sport managers.

KeyWords: Behavior of Cultural Intelligence, Sport, Manager

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